

Global Research Skills Survey

Introduction

We invite you to participate in this survey focused on career training. We seek to learn about the challenges facing researchers globally, and within specific disciplines. Your participation in this survey is completely voluntary and responses are completely confidential. Your Personal Data will not be collected. No tracking data (e.g., IP addresses, names, email addresses) or other information that can identify you is obtained either through your access to the survey or through your responses. In addition, all information you share with us will be encrypted to prevent fraudulent use. You will have the opportunity to provide your point-of-contact information, but it will be collected separately from your responses to the survey. As a result, there is no opportunity for a participant to access their survey responses, make any correction or edit to their survey responses or withdraw any information from the study as any link between your identity and your survey responses will be severed.

All of the responses will be aggregated into a summary report to provide participant experiential data for a manuscript focusing on the challenges of and opportunities for research training, with a special focus on disciplinary and geographical differences. These findings will highlight ways to better train and prepare the next generation of research scientists, representing a strategic resource for the future. This paper is being led by a team of early-career researchers associated with the Global Ecosystem Research Infrastructure (GERI) and the NSF Award 2301655, which is focused on harmonizing global data to address ecological drought. For more information about the GERI organization, please visit <https://global-ecosystem-ri.org>.

The survey will be open until **May 31st, 2025**. If you are an early-career researcher and complete the survey by *March 31st*, you will be offered the chance to enter a randomized drawing for a research training workshop (which will include professional trainings, manuscript writing and data hackathon, field trips, and more) in Summer 2025 in Boulder, CO, USA. We anticipate that it will take around 20 minutes to respond to the questions in this survey, and we look forward very much to your input on all of them. Please note that we define early-career researchers as those within 7 years of their terminal degree. We thank you very much for your time and participation. If you have any questions about the survey, please contact: contact@global-ecosystem-ri.org.

The GERI Early Career Researcher Working Group
On behalf of the global AccelNet team

Background Questions

1. Please indicate the broad disciplinary categories of your research:

Biology

Earth/Environmental Science

Chemistry

Physics

Computer Science

Mathematics

Engineering

Polar Research

Social Science

Humanities

Education

Other (please specify) _____

[Can select multiple]

2. Please describe your research sub-discipline in your own words _____

[char. limit]

3. What is your current career stage?

Undergraduate Student

Graduate Student (Masters or PhD program)

Postdoctoral Researcher

Assistant Professor

Associate or Full Professor

Research Scientist

Other (please specify) _____

4. How many years has it been since you received your terminal degree?

0–2

3–4

5–7

>7

Currently in an undergraduate degree program

Currently in a graduate degree program

5. In which country are you receiving (did you receive) your terminal degree? _____

[drop down]

6. What country are you currently based in? _____ [drop down]

Research Infrastructure (RI) Questions

7. What, in your opinion, is the best way to communicate research and training opportunities to early-career researchers around the world? _____

Email listserv

GERI Opportunities webpage

Other (please describe): _____

8. Have you been involved in research projects related to, leveraging, or enabled by a research network (such as the Long Term Ecological Research (LTER) Network or International Long Term Research Network (ILTER)), or a research infrastructure (RI; such as NEON, TERN, CERN, eLTER, ICOS, and SAEON, which compose GERI)? This could include using RI or network data, working at RI or network sites, or working as a staff member in one of these organizations.

No

No, but I would like to be involved in my future work

Yes, but not currently involved

Yes, including my current work

9. If you have not been connected to research networks or infrastructures as per above, what were the main barriers to your participation?

I did not know about them

I was not aware of one relevant to my area of expertise

I did not have the funding opportunities

I did not have the connections to join one of these projects

Something else _____

Not Applicable

[Can select multiple]

10. If you answered yes to question 7, how many of these research networks and/s and/or RI projects have you been involved in? _____

Not Applicable

11. Considering all network and RI projects that you have participated in, which year did you start this work (and end, if applicable)?

Start Year _____

End Year _____

Not Applicable

12. What was your career stage when you began working in your first network or RI project?

Not Applicable

Undergraduate Student

Graduate Student (Masters or PhD program)

Postdoctoral Researcher

Assistant Professor

Associate or Full Professor

Research Scientist

Other (please specify) _____

13. Approximately how many total personnel were directly involved in your network or RI research project(s)?

- 1–4
- 5–9
- 10–19
- 20–29
- 30+

If you have worked on multiple projects and the numbers were different across your projects, please describe this. _____

Not Applicable

14. Approximately how many members directly involved in your research project were at your same career stage when you started the project?

- 0
- 1–4
- 5+

If you have worked on multiple projects and the numbers were different across your projects, please describe this. _____

Not Applicable

15. Did you serve in a senior role, early career role, or both roles on your network or RI project(s)?

- Senior Role
- Early Career Role
- Both
- Not Applicable

16. Where have you found opportunities for training or skill development needed for participating in network or RI-enabled research projects?

- My degree program
- My college/university
- A research network or infrastructure I'm involved in
- Externally through collaborators
- Internet or other digital resources
- Teaching myself
- Other _____

Not Applicable

[Can select multiple]

17. Has your involvement in network or RI research been inhibited by access to technological infrastructure (e.g., high-performance computing, data storage), software (e.g., software license fees), or training (e.g., coding classes)?

- No
- Yes, due to technological infrastructure barriers
- Yes, due to software barriers
- Yes, due to training barriers
- Yes, due to one of these barriers, but for non-network or RI research

Not Applicable

[Can select multiple]

18. What recommendations do you have for early-career researchers interested in getting involved in network or RI-enabled research projects?

Reaching out to PIs directly

Reaching out to ECRs participating in those projects already

Writing your own proposal that utilizes network or RI data

Other _____

Not Applicable

19. In what ways did your experience working on network or RI projects help prepare you for your current position?

I learned transferable skills that I use in my position

I built foundation knowledge needed in my position

I learned about my position through my professional network resulting from this work

I do not think this work helped prepare me for my position

Other _____

Not Applicable

20. Do you have any additional feedback to share about training early-career researchers for network or RI projects?

No

Yes, _____

Not Applicable

Training Questions

Please answer the following questions with all of your research projects in mind, not just your network or RI projects (if applicable).

21. My research is primarily conducted...

- Independently with little-to-no collaboration per project
- In small teams (less than 5 collaborators per project)
- In mid-sized teams (between 5 and 10 collaborators per project)
- In large teams (typically more than 10 collaborators per project)

22. How many members of your active research projects are at the same career stage as you? *Please answer the following questions with all of your research projects in mind, not just your network or RI projects (if applicable).*

- 0
- 1-4
- 5+

23. Do you feel you have all the skills you need to be successful in research projects? *Please answer the following questions with all of your research projects in mind, not just your network or RI projects (if applicable).*

- Yes
- No

24. Barriers: What type(s) of training do/did you want but could not obtain for your research projects?

- Scientific Coding
 - Version Control
 - Citation Managers
 - Public Speaking
 - Project Management
 - Leadership
 - Mentoring
 - Field data collection
 - Data analysis
 - Statistics
 - Scientific writing/editing
 - Artificial intelligence
 - None
 - Other _____
- [Can select multiple]

25. Barriers: What prevented you from receiving that training?

No funding available

Not enough time or other scheduling constraints

Lack of advisor support

Lack of department/university support

The training was not available

Embarrassment

None

Other_____

[Can select multiple]

26. Opportunities: What kinds of skill-based training/professional development have you pursued to prepare for your research projects.

Scientific Coding

Version Control

Citation Managers

Public Speaking

Project Management

Leadership

Mentoring

Field data collection

Data analysis

Statistics

Scientific writing/editing

Artificial intelligence

None

Other_____

27. In your current or past research projects, do/did you feel prepared to mentor any students or early-career researchers involved in the skills they needed to be successful?

Yes

No

Not applicable

28. How would you rank the importance of each of the following skills for succeeding in your research project(s)?

	Not Important	Slightly Important	Moderately Important	Very Important	Extremely Important
<i>Leadership</i>					
<i>Project Management</i>					
<i>Interdisciplinary Collaboration</i>					
<i>Empathy</i>					
<i>Conflict Resolution</i>					
<i>Communication (writing)</i>					
<i>Communication (speaking)</i>					
<i>Teaching</i>					
<i>Mentorship</i>					
<i>Knowledge Dissemination/ Mobilization</i>					
<i>Data Management</i>					
<i>Statistical Analysis and/or Modeling</i>					
<i>Experimental Design</i>					
<i>Field and Laboratory Skills</i>					
<i>Artificial intelligence</i>					
<i>Work-Life Balance</i>					

29. How much training did you receive in each of the following skills while participating in your research project(s)?

	No Training Received	Some Training Received	Moderate Training Received	Lots of Training Received	Extensive Training Received
<i>Leadership</i>					
<i>Project Management</i>					
<i>Interdisciplinary Collaboration</i>					
<i>Empathy</i>					
<i>Conflict Resolution</i>					
<i>Communication (writing)</i>					
<i>Communication (speaking)</i>					
<i>Teaching</i>					
<i>Mentorship</i>					
<i>Knowledge Dissemination/ Mobilization</i>					
<i>Data Management</i>					
<i>Statistical Analysis and/or Modeling</i>					
<i>Experimental Design</i>					
<i>Field and Laboratory Skills</i>					
<i>Artificial intelligence</i>					
<i>Work-Life Balance</i>					

30. For the following skills, how did you receive that training? Select all that apply.

	Received training in a course at your institution <u>as part of your degree program</u>	Received training in a course at your institution <u>outside of your degree program</u>	Received training at a workshop or course outside your institution	Received training from your advisor in an informal setting (e.g., meetings)	Received training from someone else (e.g., postdoc) in an informal setting	Self taught	Did not receive training
<i>Leadership</i>							
<i>Project Management</i>							
<i>Interdisciplinary Collaboration</i>							
<i>Empathy</i>							
<i>Conflict Resolution</i>							
<i>Communication (writing)</i>							
<i>Communication (speaking)</i>							
<i>Teaching</i>							
<i>Mentorship</i>							
<i>Knowledge Dissemination/ Mobilization</i>							
<i>Data Management</i>							
<i>Statistical Analysis and/or Modeling</i>							
<i>Experimental Design</i>							
<i>Field and Laboratory Skills</i>							
<i>Artificial intelligence</i>							
<i>Work-Life Balance</i>							

31. After the initial training, how much have you practiced or continued using each of the following skills in your research project(s)?

	Not at all	Rarely	Moderately Often	Very Often	Extremely Often
<i>Leadership</i>					
<i>Project Management</i>					
<i>Interdisciplinary Collaboration</i>					
<i>Empathy</i>					
<i>Conflict Resolution</i>					
<i>Communication (writing)</i>					
<i>Communication (speaking)</i>					
<i>Teaching</i>					
<i>Mentorship</i>					
<i>Knowledge Dissemination/ Mobilization</i>					
<i>Data Management</i>					
<i>Statistical Analysis and/or Modeling</i>					
<i>Experimental Design</i>					
<i>Field and Laboratory Skills</i>					
<i>Artificial intelligence</i>					
<i>Work-Life Balance</i>					

32. Are there any additional skills that were not listed above that you feel are important for your research projects?

No

Yes, _____

Global Research Questions

33. How important is global scientific collaboration for solving our most pressing environmental challenges (1 being not important and 5 being extremely important) [1–5]

34. What do you think is/are the most compelling or valuable aspect(s) of international collaboration?

Data sharing

Expanding network

Exposure to new thinking/perspectives/ideas

Publications

Personal career opportunities

Working with collaborators that have skill sets that are not available locally

Accessing training opportunities that are not available locally

Accessing infrastructures (e.g. labs), equipment and/or cyberinfrastructures that are not available locally

Something else_____

[Can select multiple]

35. What kinds of trainings, workshops, and/or webinars do you think would be most useful to prepare early-career researchers for leading and participating in international projects?

Scientific Coding

Version Control

Citation Managers

Public Speaking

Project Management

Leadership

Mentoring

Field data collection

Data analysis

Statistics

Scientific writing/editing

None

Other_____

36. What do you see as the biggest barriers to international collaboration in your research? _____

No existing collaboration

Everyone in my professional network is from my country

Funding constraints or difficulties

Language differences

Scheduling or time-zone constraints

None

Other_____

37. What would you recommend as a valuable yet simple research objective using globally synchronized environmental data, if such a dataset existed? We'd love any feedback that you might have – we're hoping to collect ideas for future Global Ecosystem Research Infrastructure (GERI) initiatives._____

[char. limit]

38. Are there other barriers that have impacted your involvement in research projects (network-enabled, RI-enabled, international collaborations, or unrelated)? If so, please describe as you are comfortable._____

[no char. limit]

A separate LimeSurvey link provided at the end of the survey to keep above responses anonymous

If you would like to be entered into a randomized drawing to win a travel stipend to attend the GERI early-career researcher workshop in Summer 2025 (Boulder, CO, USA), which will involve trainings, manuscript preparation, a data hackathon, NEON field trips, and more, please provide an email address at which we can reach you if you are selected

_____.

Would you like to be contacted about future GERI research activities?

Yes

No